

ISic0052

I.Sicily inscription 0052

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. L(ucio) · Acilio · L(uci) · f(ilio) · Qui(rina)
2. Rufo
3. q(uaestori) · pro · pr(aetore) · provinc(iae)
4. Sicil(iae) · tr(ibunus) · pl(ebis) · pr(raetori)
5. praef(ecto) · frum(enti) · dand(i)
6. ex · s(enatus) · c(onsulto)
7. (vac.1)
8. Hispellates · public(e)
9. d(ecurionum) · d(ecreto)
10. patrono

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285282

EDR 127503

EDCS 22100045

Bibliography

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